

E-Learning Infrastructure And Collective Engagement: Antecedents And Conclusions In Driving E-Learning Quality

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Abstract

The objective of this study is to create a new conceptual model that aims to improve the quality of e-learning from two collective engagement variables and e-learning infrastructure to fill the gaps that exist between the variable value congruence and cognitive competence on quality e-learning effectiveness. The test statistics used in this study used five variables, namely cognitive competence, infrastructure e-learning, value congruence, collective engagement and quality e-learning. The conceptual model that has been developed in this study is tested empirically through a survey approach. The 290 respondents in this study consisted of lecturers who already had functional positions as associate professor and assistant professor at merchant colleges in Indonesia. This study adapts the e-learning theory, the results of the t test show that the results of hypothesis testing are accepted for all the proposed hypotheses and the e-learning infrastructure variable and collective engagement have been able to show their role as a mediating variable from the single test results of these two variables to become a mediator in improving quality e-learning, the results of hypothesis testing are accepted for all the proposed hypotheses. The three limitations of the research shown in this study are as follows: the first survey was only conducted at merchant colleges in Indonesia, the two studies in this study only focused on the main mediator of collective engagement and e-infrastructure. E-learning in driving quality e learning so that it does not pay attention to other theoretical aspects such as social exchange theory or other theories in education management studies, these three research surveys only try to capture perceptions of e-learning quality. From a practical perspective that can be recommended in this study, it shows that collective engagement and e-learning infrastructure can be a key strategy in improving e-learning quality, this provides recommendations for universities to encourage improvements in collective engagement and e-learning infrastructure. They will affect cognitive competence and value congruence and will ultimately increase the quality of learning.

Introduction

Beginning in 2020, many countries in the world are experiencing a global pandemic paradigm, which today has a direct impact on the education sector ((Rieley, 2020)). The education sector as a public sector has been affected by the impact of this effect, so there is a need for a pattern of changing conventional learning into non-face-to-face distance learning (UNESCO IESALC, 2020). This condition demands a cognitive consequence from the educational process organizers. to improve the scheme of the learning process ((Kaboli et al., 2017)(Parhizgar et al., 2017)(Mallat et al., 2017)(Parhizgar et al., 2017)(Kaboli et al., 2017)).

process Online learning adopted by various universities to overcome learning problems during a pandemic has caused shock therapy in the learning pattern with this online system because various lecturers and teaching staff have not been able to adapt optimally to the system ((Yu et al., 2020); (Dhawan, 2020); (Shahzad et al., 2020)). E-learning which is considered as a learning medium in hard ware and software has been deemed good enough to translate learning patterns during this pandemic. Previous research studies have provided academic criticism regarding the limitations and optimality of e-learning. E-learning, applications, communication, Internet access and electronic devices are the main infrastructure for the development of the e-learning concept ((Bączek, Zagańczyk-Bączek, Szpringer, Jaroszyński & Woźakowska-Kapłon, 2020.).In addition, there is a critical study related to the impact of ICT, which is part of e-learning. This study takes the role of e-learning infrastructure as an articulation of the need to replace conventional learning processes with online learning during this pandemic(Wang et al., 2008).

At this time e-learning for educational institutions is a necessity and a critical example for survival. so an e-learning system is needed that allows easy access to interaction between lecturers and students when industrial revolution 4.0 has been implemented in various educational institutions in the 21st century. E-learning has become a necessity for educational institutions, the development of e-learning learning systems is an embryonic product of learning models in the digital era. As a result of technological developments and innovation for the progress of the education system ((Adnan & Anwar, 2020); (Setyaningsih & Andayani, 2020); (Bączek *et Al.*, 2020.); (Narici *et al.*, 2020); (Khalil *et al.*, 2020); (Iqbal *et al.*, 2020))

The obstacles that are often faced in the distance learning process, among others, when using a distance learning system. The concept of e-learning that has not been optimally socialized. 2. The planning of the e-learning system is not good enough. 3. Limitations between students and lecturers when using e-learning infrastructure. 4. Limited facilities in supporting the e-learning program. From the description above, it has led to an academic debate from various previous researchers to provide the best solution for solving problems on the effectiveness of e-learning. In order for the implementation of distance learning to be effective, it requires socialization and sharing of knowledge about the concept of e-learning (Dhawan, 2020). The problems that often occur are the lack of expertise in both subjects and objects of study and the lack of a quality e-learning infrastructure((Al-ansi *et al.*, 2019); (Du *et al.*, 2013); (Technology, 2011)). When universities as technology makers who create reliable workforce in order to remain able to compete in the job market, universities need to adapt quickly to adopt technological advances for lecturers and educational staff but at low cost, quickly and effectively ((Liguori, 2020)). The e-learning system must be progressively carried out by educational institutions in terms of implementation and design, this depends on the capability of the institution as an organization to innovate and new technology. This new innovation and technology adoption can be implemented using a satellite system which is able to provide space for interaction between lecturers and students in online learning.((Siddiqui & Masud, 2012)). The use of hard ware such as note books, PCs, gadget and tablets is an indicator of the fulfillment of the e-learning infrastructure to answer the complexity of lecturers and students according to their respective competencies.

The success of online learning depends on the competence between students and lecturers to be able to think cognitively in using e-learning systems and applications. This is evidence of the application of technology to increase learning motivation in online learning, but contrastive studies occur when some students have incentives the greater one((Middle *et al.*, 2017)). To be involved in the learning process will tend to have the urge to learn optimally compared to students who do not have any motivation. The learning process is a complex and comprehensive activity that requires certain techniques to motivate students to analyze the characteristics of technology besides e-learning can be adopted quickly if there is experience between students and lecturers to be shared with each other((Al-ansi *et al.*, 2019)). From an organizational point of view, in this case a university, the role of lecturers and teaching staff in it has an essential role in supporting e-learning from an inter-tertiary institution. When the community is seen as a group, the community here, in this case the teachers, will have an impact on the university's strategy. Community engagement can be viewed as a pattern of activities to work collaboratively for the company, to solve problems related to social welfare from members of the organization through the groups of people in it. This is a key strategy for tertiary institutions to improve the main goals of higher education institutions at this time in realizing the effectiveness of e-learning. learning ((Bakker & Xanthopoulou, 2009)), ((Crane & Moon, 2004)) (Fawcett *et al.*, 1995)). In this study, a consequence can be found that the engagement community is the link between lecturers as teaching staff and the central community, in this case, universities to work. collaboratively to increase the effectiveness of e-learning specifically from the results of previous research studies, a work involvement built on community engagement will still increase if there is an increase in the value of craftsmanship((Fachrunnisa & Adhiatma, 2016)) ((Vogel *et al.*, 2016)). The high work involvement of a lecturer with a high enough value congruence in higher education will be able to create a community bond in it. So that it can be concluded that the value suitability will be able to drive the involvement of the group in this case the lecturer to create cognitive and progressive thinking in achieving organizational goals. The value congruence possessed by lecturers will be able to encourage the creation of work performance, this means that the work performance produced will be a benchmark for efforts to achieve goals optimally((Fachrunnisa & Adhiatma, 2016)(Vogel *et al.*, 2016)). This happens if a teacher as a human being will feel that he has a self-worth that is in accordance with the values of society, this has an impact on the perception that he is increasingly tied to the organization in which he is located . The value congruence possessed by lecturers will be able to encourage the creation of work performance, this means that the work performance produced will be a benchmark for efforts to achieve goals optimally((Albdour& Altarawneh, 2014), (Lien, 2016)). This happens if a teacher as a human being will feel that he has a self-worth that is in accordance with the values of society, this has an impact on the perception that he is increasingly tied to the organization in which he is located. The value congruence possessed by lecturers will be able to encourage the creation of work performance, this means that the work performance produced will be a benchmark for efforts to achieve goals optimally. This happens if a teacher as

a human being will feel that he has a self-worth that is in accordance with the values of society, this has an impact on the perception that he is increasingly tied to the organization in which he is located.

This study aims to measure the impact on aspects that try to increase the effectiveness of E-Learning during pandemic conditions so that universities are able to make readiness and maturity in online learning. This is done because there has been a paradigm shift in the current pandemic, namely conventional learning replaced with online learning. Distance learning is used in this study through applications and e-learning management systems. This study aims to build a debate framework for academic thinking to improve the effectiveness of distance learning. With various concepts that have been described from previous researchers, this study aims to propose a new conceptual model about the role of variable cognitive competencies(CG), e-learning infrastructure(ELF), the value congruence of lecturer(VC), collective engagement(CE) to drive quality e-learning (ELQ). This model will be tested in merchant college in Indonesia within pandemic covid-19 era.

Method

Subjects and Procedures

The subjects used in this research are lecturers who are involved in e-learning and have functional positions to teach extracurricular programs on their respective campuses. The institution chosen in this study is the technical implementation unit under the Ministry of Transportation's Maritime Transportation Human Resources Development Agency. The teaching staff selected in the sample of this study is because the teaching staff are more representative in the application of e-learning in merchant colleges. Testing the validity of the instrument in scientific quality, the initial data collection through sample studies is carried out to determine the quality of the instrument, in this case the questionnaire is used as a data collector. The initial stage was carried out for testing the face validity of 10 questionnaires that were distributed to experts, namely education management practitioners to provide a qualitative evaluation of the quality of the questionnaire. This is then used to revise the questionnaire so that the questionnaire has a fairly good number of validity and the respondent also understands the language of the questionnaire quite well. The sampling technique used was purposive sampling with the judgment sampling method. Judgment sampling selects a sample, namely teaching staff who already have functional positions and teach extracurricular programs as many as 360 questionnaires were distributed. 314 questioners were returned, 24 questionnaires could not be used because they were included in the outlier category so that only 290 questionnaires could be used for further data analysis. The level of responsiveness of 153 respondents was male and 137 respondents were female. 80 respondents have master's degrees and 20 respondents have doctor's degrees. Each scale displayed in the question item will be given measurement using an anchored scale with intervals of 1 to 10. The left most side shows the reference strongly disagrees, the right side shows a strongly agree with preference. The characteristics of the respondents are:

Table 1. Sample distribution

Gender		Tenure	
Man	A A	153	<2 Years
Woman	A a	137	2 <5 years
		24	5 <10
		75	10 <15
		15	26
Position			
Associate		87	
professor		203	
Assistant			
professor			
Qualification		Status	
	Master	195	Married
	Doctoral	95	Single
			Widower
			224
			54
			12

Validity and Reliability Testing

Researchers designed a questionnaire with 14 questions. The measure consisted of a multi-item scale adopted from previous research. Table 1 shows the variables used in our model, as well as descriptive statistics. AVE acceptance test (Average Variance Estimated). AVE which is often used is 0.50 where the AVE

value of at least 0.50 indicates a good convergent validity has the meaning that the indicator in one construct enters another variable is lower (less than 0.50) so that the probability of the indicator converges and enters the construct with the value in its block, greater than 50%. Malhotra (2006: 75) an instrument is said to be reliable if the Cronbach Alpha value is greater than or equal to 0.7", Research instruments and test results are presented in tabular form.

Table 4.2. Validity and reliability measurement

Source	Variables and Indicators	Standard estimate	Build Reliability	Average variant extracted	Legality discrimination	
Duta, 2006	Quality e learning Effectiveness		0.824	0.551	0.772	
	- orientation on user satisfaction	0.734				
	- evaluation in teaching effectiveness	0.723				
	- orientation on the implementation of academic achievements	0.746				
	- cost-effectiveness orientation	0.772				
Mezuro, 2006	Collective engagement		0.867	0.576	0.699	
	- Identification problems in a holistic manner	0.812				
	- Engage in actively seeking information	0.845				
	- Ideas for optimal problem solving	0.833				
	- et involved in the decision-making process in a potential way	0.795				
Amaral et al 2018	Value congruence		0.843	0.612	0.723	
	- brotherhood between colleagues	0.786				
	- Safety at work	0.772				
	- Authority to carry out its role	0.745				
	- Prestige/prestige in the group	0.796				
	- Autonomy in exercising its authority	0.788				
	Infrastructure e - learning		0.798	0.558	0.769	
	- Effective e-learning system	0.782				
	- Electronic devices	0.713				
	- Communication applications Internet accessibility	0.768		0.832	0.668	0.985
	Cognitive competence					
	- Pervious knowledge of online learning	0.812				
	- Skills to use e- learning systems	0.799				
	- Sufficient computer	0.806				
- Ability to communicate and Interact	0.809					
- Access to online	0.819					

The results of the validity variables. Cut value It ca variant value is greater than 0.5, and the value of discriminant validity is greater than 0.7. It can be observed that all the processed data show the required amount, as in the CC discriminant validity value 0.985; IEL = 0.769; VC = 0.723; CE = 0.699, ELQ 0.772.

at reflect the the extracted observed that

Goodness of fit Model Test

Researchers used variance-based structural equation modeling (SEM), namely, partial least-squares SEM, to analyze the data in this study the inclusion of formally measured constructs and due to our small sample size ((Evanschitzky et al., 2011)) ((Haenlein& Kaplan, 2004); ((Rigdon et al., 2017)) (Liengard et al., 2021); ((Daumiller& Dresel, 2020)) (Hafernik et al., 2021); ((Piepoli et al., 2016)). Goodness of Fit Model criteria, χ^2 (Chi-Square) = 125.05, Significant Probability = 0.215, GFI = 0.914, AGFI = 0.987, TLI = 0.962, CFI = 0.942, RMSEA = 0.02 By looking at the RMSEA figure that is less than 0.08. And although the GFI, TLKI and CFI figures show a figure greater than 0.9, there is no problem with the arrangement of the model.

Hypothesis Test

The next step is testing the hypothesis for the causal relationship between variables using the CR-Critical ratio criteria equal to or greater than 2.0 ((Arbuckle, 2016). Then testing the empirical analysis model (output model).

The external model is a model that determines the relationship between latent constructs and In other words, the hypothesis defines how each indicator is related to the other latent constructs, as described in the Table.

Hypothesis	Standard Estimates	Critical Ratio	P-Value	Result
Cognitive Competence → E-learning Infrastructure	0,695	9,519	0,000	Supported
E-learning Infrastructure → E-learning Quality	0,709	2,789	0,000	Supported
Value Congruence → Collective Engagment	0,804	2,887	0,000	Supported
Collective Engagment → E-Learning Quality	0,689	2,956	0,000	Supported
Cognitive Competence → E-learning Infrastructure	6,72345		0,000	Supported
E-learning Infrastructure → E-learning Quality				
Value Congruence → Collective Engagment	6,83421		0,000	Supported
Collective Engagment → E-Learning Quality				

Hypothesis Test

The CFA model that has been tested is then converted into a structural model to test these hypotheses research. Table 3 shows the test results. All hypotheses were validated with a significant level of $p < 0.001$. Additionally, the path regression coefficient for H1 = 0.695; H2 = 0.709; H3 = 0.804; and H4 = 0.689, with a critical ratio or t-value > 2.0. It shows it that the test results of all proposed hypotheses are accepted.

Mediating Effect

Test results The IEL mediation effect on the relationship between CC and ELQ has been tested using. The Sobel Test ((Hayes & Hayes, 2009)). The statistical test of the Z value of the test results obtained a value of 6.72645. While the mediation effect of CE which is contained in the relationship between VC and ELQ, the results of statistical tests to determine the mediation effect obtained a value of 6.84231 where the result is higher than the cut-off value of 1.96. This indicates a mediating effect of the variables tested. In other words, CE and IEL have mediated the impact of VC on ELQ and CC on ELQ.

Results and Discussion

Regarding the learning process during the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020 and 2021. The first study is related to the ability of universities to adopt standardized distance learning applications. Analyze the role of antecedent variables in diversifying the quality of distance learning using e-learning. By taking the sample at a merchant college under the Ministry of Transportation, the sample was used to test an empirical research model to drive the quality of distance learning with e-learning. The results showed that cognitive competence affected infrastructure and distance learning using e-learning. The cognitive abilities possessed by students and lecturers in recognizing learning with the concept of e-learning require the ability to have skills in using e-learning systems, sufficient experience in operating computers or gadgets, this will lead to the ability to communicate and interact and access online. If this cognitive ability becomes the core for the competence of students and lecturers, it will be able to optimize the use of all e-learning infrastructure and this will significantly increase the teaching ability of lecturers, cost-effectiveness, user satisfaction, in this case, lecturers and students, and increase academic achievement. This can drive the quality of distance learning with e-learning. In addition to the extent aspect, there are also inherent aspects, namely the role of the teaching staff in providing grades and attachment for fellow teachers to improve the quality of the distance learning system. This value, among others, can be in the form of an equivalent value.

The value of equality that is built by fellow lecturers will be able to build a collective link between them ((Lien, 2016)). Feelings of autonomy, altruism, the friendship between peers, and the prestige or prestige possessed by each lecturer will be able to influence the value of having a sense of mutual attachment. This mutual bonding can be manifested in the form of identifying problems that occur, always trying to be involved in finding new information, having progressive ideas in solving problems, and encouraging to always be involved in the decision-making process within the institution. e-learning strategies to convey knowledge in the digital age noted that one of the advantages of e-learning in education is its focus on e-learning. This mutual bonding can be manifested in the form of identifying problems that occur, always trying to be involved in finding new information, having progressive ideas in solving problems, and encouraging to always be involved in the decision-making process within the institution.

This study provides a form of contribution to academic rationality in showing the factors that affect the quality of E-learning. The attribute variable attributes previously described are the existence of the factors driving the quality of e-learning in commercial universities in Indonesia. In particular, the quality of e-learning services has been demonstrated by indicators, namely the quality of the e-learning system, the quality of e-learning support and administration services, the quality of instructors, and special e-learning materials((Al-ansi et al., 2019); (Du et al., 2013); (Technology, 2011)). The implications taken from this study have been able to pay special attention to the quality of e-learning systems. In an e-learning environment, learning that is carried out on learning subjects is emphasized more on cohesive interactions between students and their learning systems. He can also consider the quality of the e-learning system as the quality of e-learning which includes software and hardware capabilities to meet online learning needs((Siddiqui & Masud, 2012)). Higher education institutions must provide competent software and hardware to support the smoothness and reliability of the e-learning system. Items that make up the quality of e-learning are predominantly influenced by the ease of use, privacy security, and accuracy of the system.

A well-organized organizational structure must also be realized by lecturers and students. Good enough relationship between lecturers and students, this can be realized through fairly effective coordination due to the equality of values and collective linkages between each lecturer and student, the impact of value congruence and collective engagement will be able to encourage cognitive understanding to prepare concepts supportive technology and fun learning conditions for students and lecturers((Albdour& Altarawneh, 2014)),((Lien, 2016)).The results of this study have identified the effect of value congruence on the involvement of teachers who hold high values in the organization who tend to have autonomous motivation in wanting to be involved in solving problems in the organization. This can be applied optimally if these values have high values and the level of motivation is controlled. This happens because of the form of collective control of educators in carrying out a comparative analysis of their personal values and workplaces in the places where they work. Lecturers, through the values they have in their institutions, tend to be consistent with their organizational values and tend to experience a form of fulfilling psychological needs. Students currently have good technology so that they can encourage the realization of the quality of e-learning through interest and satisfaction with the e-learning system, a scientific argument can be recommended to improve learning systems through the safety and security of students' data and information that they have to consider carefullyadequate. If this information is unsafe then there will be negative academic consequences that affect students and universities((Al-ansi et al., 2019)). Higher education must continue to provide a holistic safety system for students to increase the level of legitimacy that can be trusted in the e-learning system. The accuracy of the e-learning system must be considered well enough, the information displayed on the learning website must be accurate, easy to access.

Conclusion

The results of this study contribute to the concept of improving the quality of distance learning with e-learning, especially in higher education institutions, based on the results of the discussion above, this study leads to the concept of value, linkages, mastery of e-learning infrastructure, and affective commitment owned by lecturers to improve the quality of e-learning. The results showed that affective commitment affected e-learning infrastructure and e-learning infrastructure affected the quality of distance learning with e-learning. This shows that each of the e-learning infrastructure variables is one of the key strategies for improving the quality of distance learning. In addition, a sense of collective attachment can also be a key strategy for improving the quality of distance learning.

Recommendations

E-learning infrastructure and collective engagement are variables that can drive the quality of distance learning. This implies that these two concepts are core competencies to improve the quality of distance learning, including: The survey was only conducted at merchant colleges under the Ministry of Transportation in Indonesia. This study only focuses on a renewal concept in quantitative research designs using mediation as a solution to solving problems. Namely, using e-learning infrastructure mediation and collective engagement. However, this research succeeded in proving a new empirical research mode as an integrated approach model for solving problems related to the quality of distance learning with e-learning. Future research suggests integrating variables and theories to expand this research model, for example involving the team's ability to solve educational institution problems related to online learning. Future researchers can also explore the presence of various moderators who are outside this research.

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